

FEATURES OF IMMUNOGLOBULIN E AND BLOOD PROTEIN ALTERATIONS IN PEDIATRIC BRONCHOPULMONARY PATHOLOGY

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Abstract. *This study presents an analysis of serum total protein and immunoglobulin E (IgE) levels in young children diagnosed with respiratory diseases. Significant associations were identified between the severity of inflammation and changes in biochemical and immunological parameters. The findings demonstrate that children with pneumonia exhibit more pronounced alterations, indicating the potential role of IgE and total protein as markers for evaluating disease severity.*

Keywords: *total protein, pneumonia, Immunoglobulin E, Vitamin D, bronchitis, children, inflammation.*

Introduction

Respiratory diseases of children in young ages remains one of the most common reasons for seeking medical attention and hospitalization in pediatric practice. Among the pathogenetic mechanisms of the inflammatory process, increasing attention is paid to immunological and metabolic disorders [1, 2].

Immunoglobulin E (IgE) plays a key role in the development of immediate hypersensitivity, and is also involved in antihelminthic protection and immune responses in herpesvirus infections and a number of immunodeficiency states [3, 4]. At the same time, the level of total protein serves as an indicator of the state of protein metabolism and reflects the compensatory reactions of the body during inflammation [5].

Despite a large number of studies, a comprehensive assessment of IgE and total protein in acute inflammatory lung diseases in children remains poorly understood.

Objective of the study

To assess the levels of immunoglobulin E and total blood protein in children with acute inflammatory diseases of the respiratory system (pneumonia and bronchitis) with an analysis of their relationship with the clinical manifestations of the disease.

Materials and methods of the study

The main group (group 1) consisted of 33 patients (55.5%) with an established diagnosis of community-acquired pneumonia, confirmed by clinical signs and radiographic changes corresponding to inflammatory processes in the lung tissue. The comparison group (group 2) consisted of 27 children (44.5%) with a diagnosis of acute bronchitis, verified on the basis of the clinical picture and auscultation data. A clinical examination with anamnesis, physical examination and laboratory tests (complete blood count and urine analysis, total protein level), immunological determination of IgE and vitamin D concentrations, as well as chest radiography and, if indicated, multispiral computed tomography (MSCT) were conducted. The diagnoses were

formulated on the basis of current international classifications and clinical protocols (GOLD, ESPID, AAP). The obtained data were processed using statistical programs, with subsequent comparative analysis of the studied parameters between the groups.

Results of the study

Analysis of the obtained results revealed that in terms of gender composition in both groups, boys predominated (in group 1 - 55.5%, in group 2 - 61.1%) (Fig. 1). Analysis of the age composition showed that the largest proportion in the studied sample were children aged 2 to 3 years - 61.2%, while children aged 1 to 2 years made up 38.8% (Fig. 2).

Figure 1. Distribution of examined children by gender

Figure 2. Distribution of examined children depending on age.

Children with pneumonia had more severe clinical symptoms (Table 1) and higher IgE values compared to children with bronchitis ($p < 0.05$) (Table 2)

Symptoms	Group 1 (pneumonia)	Group 2 (bronchitis)
Fever	90%	60%
Cough	100%	100%
Shortness of breath	75%	35%
Wheezing on auscultation	85%	70%

Table 1. Frequency of symptoms in children with pneumonia and bronchitis

There was also a statistically significant increase in the level of total protein, which may be associated with the acute phase response of the body. Vitamin D levels were significantly lower in children with pneumonia 18 ± 5 ng / ml, compared with control values and children with bronchitis 25 ± 6 ng / ml

Indicator	Norm	Group 1 (pneumonia)	Group 2 (bronchitis)
Immunoglobulin E (IU/ml)	up to 60	120 ± 15	85 ± 10
Total protein (g/l)	65–85	90 ± 8	78 ± 7
Vitamin D (ng/ml)	30–100	18 ± 5	25 ± 6

Table 2. Comparative laboratory parameters

In addition, an increase in IgE was associated with higher total protein levels, which may indicate protein hyperproduction in response to antigen stimulation [5].

Additional analysis of the obstetric history revealed significant differences between the groups (Fig. 3). Mothers of children from the pneumonia group had significantly more frequent episodes of acute respiratory viral infections (88.2% versus 61.2%) and TORCH infections (44.8% versus 12.3%), which may indicate the influence of antenatal infectious and inflammatory factors on the immune reactivity of the fetus. These women were also more often diagnosed with early toxicosis of pregnancy (94.2%) compared to mothers of children from the bronchitis group (86.2%). It should be noted that mild anemia during pregnancy was more often recorded in the 2nd group (48.7%), which may reflect differences in the nutritional structure or the level of perinatal medical care (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Comparative analysis of obstetric history in mothers of children in two groups (%)

Analysis of concomitant diseases in the examined children revealed a number of significant differences. Patients with pneumonia more often had conditions such as: rickets (54.6% versus 40.7%), mild anemia (68.4% versus 52.2%), acute nasopharyngitis and chronic tonsillitis. (Fig.4)

Figure 4. Concomitant diseases in children with pneumonia and bronchitis (%)

Higher prevalence of protein-energy malnutrition (PEM) in children with bronchitis (18.2%) compared to the pneumonia group (7.4%), which may be associated with a higher proportion of viral etiological factors in the pathogenesis of the disease.

Analysis of the studies revealed that:

- An increase in IgE levels correlates with the severity of the clinical picture.
- IgE levels correlated positively with the concentration of total protein and negatively with the level of vitamin D.
- Children with pneumonia showed a more pronounced deviation of these indicators than children with bronchitis.

Discussion

Immunoglobulin E can act as an additional biomarker reflecting the degree of inflammatory response in the respiratory tract [6]. At the same time, the concomitant increase in total protein confirms the presence of an active phase of inflammation. Vitamin D deficiency associated with high IgE is consistent with data on its immunomodulatory role and impact on the severity of infectious diseases of the respiratory tract [7].

The obtained results correspond to the conclusions of previous studies, which emphasize the importance of IgE not only as an allergic marker, but also as a universal immunological indicator in acute inflammatory conditions in children [8, 9].

Conclusion.

The results of the study showed that the level of immunoglobulin E in children with pneumonia is significantly higher than in the control and significantly higher than in bronchitis, which can be used to assess the severity of the inflammatory process. A positive correlation was found between IgE and total protein and a negative one with the level of vitamin D, which reflects metabolic and immune changes against the background of inflammation. The results show the feasibility of including the determination of IgE and total protein in a comprehensive laboratory assessment of bronchopulmonary diseases in young children.

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